

PROSPECTS FOR INCREASING THE ROLE OF ELECTRONIC SERVICES IN ENSURING SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL ECONOMY AND FURTHER IMPROVING THE SECTOR

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Annotation

This dissertation presents information on the prospects for increasing the role of electronic services in ensuring sustainable development of the digital economy and further improvement of the industry compared to the current state. The main issues of development of innovative forms of electronic commerce are considered. The ways of further improvement of the current state of electronic commerce in Uzbekistan are described, and we will also consider what methods can be used to develop this industry in the country today.

Key words: field of electronic services, economic development, small businesses, progress of electronic commerce, process of e-commerce.

Introduction

The development of e-commerce in our country is an integral part of the large-scale economic reforms being implemented in our country. Thus, thanks to the adopted laws on the development of e-commerce and the adaptation of the economy to the process of informatization, decisions of the President and Government, and the created technological foundations, the e-commerce market has formed in Russia. In recent years, and the mechanisms that serve it have been systematically improved.

For the first time in our country, a law in the field of electronic services was adopted on April 29, 2004 and regulated by the Law "On Electronic Commerce", which was updated in 2015 and 2022. According to the law, electronic transactions must provide buyers with the following information about the seller:

- the full name of the legal entity indicating the organizational and legal form or the last name, first name and patronymic of an individual;
- postal address and email address, information on the state registration of the company;
- the presence of a license in cases stipulated by law;
- the procedure for concluding an agreement in electronic commerce;

- the possibility and procedure for making changes and additions to the terms of the agreement for the provision of electronic services;
- the procedure for sending and revoking acceptance;
- terms of delivery and payment for goods (including works, services), as well as the prices offered for them (including the applicable tariffs);
- indicators of the conditions included in the agreement by referring to an electronic document posted on a publicly available information resource;
- it is necessary to keep records of all electronic documents and messages.

The Cabinet of Ministers is responsible for the implementation of state policy and programs in the field of electronic services and coordinates the activities of state bodies in this area. The Cabinet of Ministers has vested the Ministry of Digital Technologies with special powers to supervise the field of electronic commerce and electronic services.

It should be emphasized that the opportunities for the development of electronic communications in Uzbekistan are growing every year. Its development creates an opportunity for our domestic producers to open new markets and find new customers. Following the chosen and current path of development of the electronic services sphere will allow the economy of our country to become one of the leading representatives of the world market in the future. The fact that Uzbekistan has chosen the right way to solve existing problems in the sphere of electronic services is reflected in the well-being of the people, the progress of our society, our economic development. At the same time, the supplier of electronic services and the electronic trader play an important role in expanding the opportunities of small businesses operating in our country. Today, the government bodies of Uzbekistan adhere to the following principles, widely used in the world experience of developing electronic services:

- the corporate sector should play an active role in the development of electronic services;
- it is necessary to prevent the introduction of various unreasonable restrictions on electronic trade communications by government bodies;
- a government agency can interfere in the process of electronic commerce in order to support entities in this sphere and improve the legal framework;
- when developing measures to manage the sphere of electronic services, a government agency must take into account the features of the Internet;
- the process of e-commerce can take place on a global scale, regardless of administrative-territorial division and state borders.

Conclusion

In conclusion, a clear and coordinated strategy is needed to develop the e-services infrastructure and create an online environment in the country, provide incentives, create a skilled and modern workforce, invest in infrastructure, and establish strong international relations. By following these strategies, our country can create an environment that is more conducive to the e-services industry and promote economic growth and development.

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